

careables.org

Deliverable 3.2

Platform v2

including

documentation tool

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the second phase of WP3 'Platform & Tooling' both, user research and co-design, informed the development of the platform that is mainly aimed to provide information and online tools to the multiple users of Careables.

The platform consists of two online instances: The careables.org website is the main point of entrance for the project and the place where visitors are guided towards information based on their background, interests and needs. The Welder platform, welder.app, is the place where the open healthcare products are shared. It is the place for documentation, files, and offers also the possibility for online collaborate on shared artefacts.

The two instances of the platform can be accessed individually via www.careables.org and via www.welder.app/careables. They are also cross-linked and the users can navigate easily between the two instances. Based on user feedback the platforms are continuously updated and improved, not only in terms of content, but also in its features that they offer and in terms of usability.

Careables is also actively involved in the definition and implementation of an Open standard for open hardware documentation. We are contributing to the discussions of an expert group that is working under the title "Open Know How". The group is developing an open standard for documenting and sharing projects, with the purpose to increase discoverability, portability, and translatability of knowledge relating to making hardware (physical objects). We intend to implement the standard into the welder.app/careables platform as long as it is supportive of its purpose.

This document is structured the following way: first we provide some introduction and background information for the platform development, then we describe how the work of this work package relates with the other work packages of the Careables project and how this work is a joint effort. We then continue to describe the co-design process process, followed by a description of the functionalities of the resulting platform. Details on the user testing of the platform will be presented in more detail in the deliverables of work package 4 - impact assessment. A final outlook presents the further plans for platform adjustments for the final year of the funding period.

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
CONTENTS	3
List of figures	4
List of tables	4
List of abbreviations	4
1. Introduction	5
1.1 BACKGROUND	5
1.2 OBJECTIVES	6
1.3 THE PLATFORM	6
1.4 CONTRIBUTION AND OTHER WPS	7
2. Careables.org	10
2.1 DESIGN PROCESS	11
2.2 CAREABLES.ORG V2	14
2.3 FUTURE STEPS	17
3. Welder	18
3.1 TIMEFRAME FOR 2019	18
3.2 WELDER FUNCTIONALITY	19
3.3 OPEN SOURCE	20
3.4 FUTURE STEPS	21
ANNEX	23
Annex 1: Personas and user journey	24
Annex 2: Welder Functionality	45

List of figures

- Figure 1: Connection with WPs
- Figure 2: Brainstorming about Careables.org at OpenDot
- Figure 3: Timeline
- Figure 4: Careables.org homepage
- Figure 5: Careables.org numbers of the first 3 months
- Figure 6: Design for care collection on Welder.app
- Figure 7: Diagram of Welder's system architecture

List of tables

- Table 1: Overview of Careables.org v2 features
- Table 2: Overview

List of abbreviations

AH	Agile Heap
CAPPSI	Collective Awareness Platforms for Sustainability and Social Innovation
CM	Consortium meeting
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering
KUL	KU Leuven
OPEN	OpenDot
TOG	Together to Go Foundation
WAAG	WAAG society
WEV	Wevolver
WP	Work Package
ZSI	Centre for Social Innovation

1. Introduction

Careables is a social innovation project that puts in connection health and care field with digital fabrication with the aims of fostering the autonomy of people with disabilities and consequently impacting positively on their lives. Since it is embedded within CAPSSI initiative, the project offers an online environment where documented solutions - from simple hacks of existing objects to tech prosthetics - are made available. We call them careables.

Despite the great heterogeneity, all solutions have common ground because:

- they are addressed to people with disabilities - both adults and children with special needs or physical limitations - and their caregivers;
- they are mostly created by a team of makers, designers, people with disabilities and healthcare professionals;
- they are replicable thanks to open documentation, which includes assembly guides, bill of materials and design files.

Also, co-design is the guiding principle of the overall project: diverse skills, competences, knowledge, and experiences gather to come to something new and meaningful. Codesign happens throughout all Careables project: during consortium meetings, Open calls or the Health&care Summer School (WP 1) to create a careable or in the development of the platform itself.

This document describes the activities of the second-year project and is organized as follows:

- Section 1 presents the project, summarizes goals and the advancement concerning Deliverable 3.1 *Platform v1 including documentation tool*;
- Section 2 is about Careables.org based on Wordpress, its design process and completely new layout;
- Section 3 is dedicated to the new repository and documentation tool hosted on Welder.app.

1.1 BACKGROUND

As stated in Deliverable 3.1 *Platform v1 including documentation tool*, during the first year WP 3 Platform & Tooling concentrated mainly on research in order to frame the context in which careables is operating: (1) its players, (2) its

beneficiaries (3) its multidimensionality - revolving around various topics such as design, healthcare, digital manufacturing, laws, sustainable development, communities of practise.

From the benchmark of existing collaborative platforms and their documentation tools to interviews with therapists, from the co-design session held in Eindhoven with all the consortium members to the survey sent out in October 2018, we explored different aspects connected especially to online collaborative communities which brought us to the creation of a platform that was based on two systems:

- **Wordpress structure** launched in April 2018 that is the official entry point to careables and functions mainly as a communication channel with blog posts, events, and general information about the project;
- **Wevolver structure** that is the Careables database for solutions and hosts the documentation tool v1.

1.2 OBJECTIVES

The second phase of WP3 Platform & Tooling has the following objectives:

- to outline the profiles of potential platform users, meaning their needs, motivations, goals, and behaviours;
- to shape the platform's structure, interface and layout taking into account who potential careables users are;
- to increase people's knowledge about co-design, digital fabrication technologies and their wide application to disabilities and healthcare sector through useful contents and tools;
- to shift towards an open standard for documentation by a new improved tool to be tested during next co-design sessions;
- to provide a fully open source repository of careables, organized by the taxonomy categories developed by WP2 and presented in *Deliverable 2.1 Open Healthcare map v1*;
- to gather valuable feedback about the platform from actual users while they explore it.

1.3 THE PLATFORM

The platform needs to perform various functions for various types of people and has different purposes. These groups are care recipients and their carers; healthcare professionals; designers, engineers, makers.

The functions of the platform can grossly be divided between:

- provide information;
- provide both access to documentation and files of the healthcare solution projects, and an online collaboration environment.

Therefore, the platform consists of **two online instances**. The **Careables.org** website is the main point of entrance for the project, and the place where visitors are guided to information based on their background and needs (lead: OpenDot). The **Welder.app** platform is the place where documentation, files, and the possibility to collaborate online on healthcare solutions reside (lead: Wevolver).

Initially, the Careables environment was envisioned as a part of Wevolver.com, the platform developed by the consortium partner Wevolver. However, the goals of Wevolver and the environment for documenting and collaborating on open source hardware are different. We learned that trying to incorporate both needs into a single platform resulted in 1) overly complicated and less reliable software and 2) a greater challenge to provide users with the right information and guidance.

Therefore, we decided to continue the development of the documentation and collaboration environment on a new web application, namely Welder. This improved the performance of the platform and increased the speed with which functionality could be developed.

Welder - as a platform - is open for other organizations and individuals to use as well. This positions the platform in the wider maker and open-source hardware community and has several benefits related also to the sustainability of the project, including:

- Careables has its own dedicated environment on Welder;
- Careables can be discovered by more people, widening the dissemination of both the project and the careables, and increasing the number of potential developers of careables solutions;
- Careables' design solutions can be used in other projects, and vice versa, that means that careables can also leverage design solutions from non-careable projects.

1.4 CONTRIBUTION AND OTHER WPs

The implementation of WP3 *Platform & Tooling* is a consortium effort driven by co-design methodology and complementarity of knowledge, skills, and experiences, operating in connection with all the other WPs.

In order to result in a tangible achievement, OpenDot is responsible for coordinating and providing the technical work plan to all the partners inside WP3. Besides management, as explained in section 1.3, OpenDot’s tasks regard the design, development, iteration, and testing of Careables.org, while Wevolver leads the creation of Welder, the open-source documentation tool.

Then, task allocations and roles correspond to partners’ profiles and mutually integrate the activities carried out in different WPs, intending to ensure continual cooperation, as well as reaching the project’s objectives.

The image outlines the interdependencies between WP3 and the other WPs, then roles and contributions to the platform.

Figure 1: Connection with WPs

In details:

- **WP1:** The platform integrates the solutions developed during the Open calls organized by Waag ([Welder.app/Design for care collection](https://welder.app/design-for-care-collection)), makes available the training kit addressed to entities interested in applying the co-design approach ([Careables.org/Resources](https://careables.org/resources)) and promotes meet-ups and presentations ([Careables.org/News and events](https://careables.org/news-and-events)).
- **WP2:** The platform integrates both the Open Healthcare Map included in Deliverable 2.1, presenting both the final taxonomy and the best practices of solutions from existing repositories, and co-designed careables ([Welder.app/Design for care collection](https://welder.app/design-for-care-collection)).
- **WP4:** Through the user tests led by ZSI, the platform acquires useful data and feedback which will contribute to the next release.
- **WP5:** Contents for the platform are provided by WP5 because it is conceived to be a powerful communication tool to spread careables approach thanks to concrete results, stories of people behind projects, materials, documents, toolkits to learn more, and events organised or recommended by the consortium ([Careables.org](https://careables.org)). The platform also links to official Careables social networks (Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter).
- **WP6:** The platform takes on the findings included in *Deliverable 6.1* and *Deliverable 6.2* with reference to product liability, the privacy of users' data (ie. avoiding cookies) and intellectual property rights connected to careables solutions ([Welder.app/template to upload careables](https://welder.app/template-to-upload-careables)).

Moreover, all partners have provided input to structure the platform considering aspects such as architecture, language, user experience, and content.

2. Careables.org

Figure 2: Brainstorming about Careables.org at OpenDot

As stated in the project proposal, careables is a “repository of co-created health care solutions improving the quality of life of people with disabilities”. In the implementation of the project - as we approached our target groups and talked with them during a meet up (WP 1), a codesign session (WP 2) or just after a public presentation in a conference (WP 5) - we realized that, although movement of maker of health is already taking place, there are still some challenges and resistances. In fact, healthcare practitioners often don't see the advantages of technologies but they are rather scared by them, the world of fab labs, makerspaces and hackerspaces are somehow embedded, co-designing doesn't represent a common approach and makers are unaware of the possibility to create something useful for a person with a disability.

Borrowing the terminology from the *Diffusion of innovations* theory by sociologist Everett Rogers, Careables can more easily address to *early adopters* and

innovators, so people that, thanks to their educational, social, financial resources, are proactive to change and willing to use technologies. What about the others? Following this lesson learned, before having a careables community that develops, shares and replicates, we must get people involved.

The new careables.org objectives are:

- to inspire: people need to see themselves represented and to feel that something is possible, that their personal or professional life can improve.
- to get involved: people need to acquire the knowledge or skills to do something, to understand things they don't know and get introduced to new concepts.

Within this framework, Carebles.org is the missing enabler and can represent leverage to foster engagement. Therefore, we designed it keeping the people at the center of the process.

2.1 DESIGN PROCESS

Over the second year implemented activities comprise multiple stages, from summing up all the information gathered during the research phase to reframe platform's objectives, to re-design the overall structure and identity, in order to eventually get to the launch of Careables.org v2. The applied methodology is based on user experience design discipline, which takes into account the heterogeneous typology of target groups - namely makers, designers, engineers, people in search for a solution and their carers, and healthcare professionals - and provides adequate answers to their requests in terms of content and visual aspects.

The following timeline details the project planning and all the activities carried out:

Figure 3: Timeline

Hereby, a brief overview of the chosen process:

1. Survey analysis: from the online surveys distributed between October and November 2019, we collected 99 responses of makers, 74 responses of healthcare professionals and 26 responses of people with disabilities and their carers (total: 199 responses). The in-depth analysis of the results highlighted valuable insight of user groups' behaviors, experiences, needs towards health and care issues, co-design methodology, making, and information websites (ie. dialogue, reliability, support, and understandability were key-aspects underlined by all target groups). This helped in the identification of the overall platform strategy.

2. Consortium meeting in Milan: following the outcomes of Eindhoven co-design session, during the consortium meeting in Milano of February 2020 we evaluated the strengths and weaknesses of Careables platform and jointly redefined its main goal, that is not simply replicating individual projects but rather, encouraging the replication of co-design approach by inspiring others to do it.

3. Personas and user journey: we integrated the results of the survey analysis into producing careables' personas, which are fictional but realistic representations of target users, with their objectives and research motivations. Then, we designed the journey maps of each persona to outline (a) users' behaviors, (b) how the platform engages with them and how it helps them in reaching a specific goal (see *Annex 1* for further details).

4. Architecture: building from the personas and user journeys, as well as benchmarking websites related to co-design for care, we defined the sitemap describing both the hierarchy of content and the navigation structure of careables website (home page and sections). Two criteria were chosen: ease of navigation and user-friendliness.

5. Wireframes: we created a digital prototype of Careables.org using the design tool *Figma*. This allows us to have an interactive presentation of the user interface to make the consortium partners understand the navigability, functionality and design identity concept.

6. Consortium meeting in Berlin: we discussed the wireframes all together, took notes of feedback concerning language, page layout elements, and sections and then assigned tasks and roles for the next content creation.

7. Careables.org development: after the consolidation of the wireframes, we dealt with both designing and coding of the platform: on one side we shaped the pages' layouts graphically (color scheme, fonts, structure of information, menu, bars, images, and videos) and on the other side we built the front-end and back-end based on WordPress, implementing a tailored theme, limiting the number of plugins and adding features and interactivity.

8. Content creation: simultaneously with the website creation, we worked on content, writing headlines and text, editing and adapting existing materials from the migration of careables.org v1.

9. Editor guidelines: as careables.org is a dynamic platform and is continuously fed by all consortium partners with the coordination of GIG, we prepared basic guidelines to facilitate the upload of news, events, and stories.

10. 2nd release: after review of the entire website and deployment, the new platform was officially launched on 1st October 2019 followed by the communication campaign on social networks

11. Fixing and implementation: by using *Trello* board, each partner can track any problems faced while navigating, from bugs to not working links, up to wish list features, that are then prioritized and eventually fixed or integrated.

12. User tests: conceived by ZSI, the interviews involved potential users in structured interviews with predefined tasks to be solved.

2.2 CAREABLES.ORG V2

Figure 4: Careables.org homepage

Based on the design process, the new Careables.org structure is outlined as follows:

Homepage: the landing page opens with *careables* definition - invented by Careables project itself - and images of both people making and solutions. Then, it

explains the idea of co-design and its process and clarifies who are the target groups:

- I have a healthcare need: a person with disability and caregiver;
- I am a healthcare professional: nurses, doctors, researchers in the health and care fields, therapists and practitioners in general;
- I like tinkering: makers, designers, engineers;
- I am just curious: a person interested or working in a social innovation sector.

It ends with a series of featured carebles classified in 3 categories (*careables we codesigned*, *careables of the month* and *careables for fun and leisure*) and the call-to-action.

Also, the sections are:

About: it gives information about the project background, the methodology behind and organisations of the consortium.

Resources: it contains useful materials divided into 6 typologies meant to increase the knowledge, awareness, and skills of the target groups.

Stories: it aims to empathize and develop a warmer and deeper understanding of what a careables is, and the process to create it from the words of people taking part in the change

Discover careables: it presents visually careables taxonomy to orientate the research of visitors, guides them to the sign-up page where they can upload a project, and links directly to Welder for further information about each careable.

News&Events: it highlights a collection of relevant news and events, both from the consortium partners, and other relevant organizations

The new version of Careables.org have distinctive features which are concisely summarized in the table below:

Table 1: Overview of Careables.org v2 features

Careables.org v2	
Personas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● care recipients (people with physical limitations) and their carers; ● healthcare professionals; ● designers, engineers, makers; ● stakeholders engaged mainly in social innovation programmes (ie. public entities, universities, foundations)

Key-aspects

Specificity: all solutions on careables.org belong to health and care domains, are meant to preserve people's independence and are created employing digital fabrication technologies.

Engagement: through stories, people - whether they are personally or professionally interested in the project - can find value and answers to their needs.

Empowerment: by the exchange of open knowledge, the platform enables people to be proactive.

Awareness: innovation is not accepted by default and careables.org helps people become technologically/health literate and increase confidence about the potentials.

Collaboration: there's a broad ecosystem of organisations already working on the same topic and so careables.org is there to give them visibility.

Openness: it is the principle implied in the maker movement and the platform guarantees free access to content and documentation.

Co-design: it is the adopted approach in the creation of meaningful careables, as well as in the development of the platform itself.

Technical features

Accessibility: the online environment is conceived to be user-friendly and first changes in fonts and colours have been implemented in this direction.

Deployment: simplified architecture, redefinition of sections, tailored WordPress theme, fewer plug-ins are structural aspects of Careables.org v2.

User-centred design: contents, navigation and graphic layout are conceived to satisfy the preferences that the different typology of personas may have.

2.3 FUTURE STEPS

Figure 5: careables.org numbers of the first 3 months (accessed: 18th December 2019)

As highlighted in the picture above, although only 3 months have passed since its official launch, Careables.org v2 is getting good results in terms of interest by external visitors and we are currently working to provide them with more and more compelling content and the easiest navigation.

As to the next year, also based on the feedback emerged during the user tests, we are planning two more releases (June 2020 and October 2020). In detail, we are going to work on:

- stronger Careables.org visual identity;
- new features like a *Help button* to guide people in understanding the aims and opportunities of Careables.org;
- optimisation for mobile and tablet;
- improvement of website visibility in search engines.

3. Welder

3.1 TIMEFRAME FOR 2019

Table 2: Overview

Done in 2019	From:	To:
User authentication system	January	January
New, extended version of the project creation template	February	April
Feature for adding and editing text files	August	September
New text editor software for all creation and editing features	October	October
Codebase refactoring and documentation to enable complete open sourcing	November	November
Continuous software performance and stability improvements and bug fixes	January	November
Continuous iterative user interface and styling improvements	January	November

3.2 WELDER FUNCTIONALITY

Figure 6: Design for care collection on Welder.app

Welder is an open platform to share the project's documentation to empower communities with file sharing and a version management solution. Hereby its core features:

Two types of projects

1-pagers: It is an agile format to collect the basic information of an existing project (that is located on another online platform or website like Thingiverse or Instructables) and to link to its full documentation.

Full Documentation: It is the complete step-by-step format conceived for anyone willing to share his/her projects on Welder or co-designed within Careables project..

Project Creation Template

This template guides users in the creation of a project. It provides them with specific fields for the essential information of a project documentation.

File Sharing

Welder provides users the ability to add any type of file to their project documentation. There is a previewer which renders various file types in the browser. For example, 3D files can be viewed online.

Texts

Users can create text files to further add information to their project. The texts can be edited and viewed in the browser.

Assembly Guides

To explain how a project is put together, users can create a step by step guide with instructions, images, and videos. The assembly guides furthermore contain meta-information about the assembly process: difficulty, time requirements, components used, tools and fabrication machines. These can all be filled in by the creator of the project.

Version control

Welder contains a version control functionality based on 'Git'. Git is a file storage system that tracks changes in a set of files. It is the de-facto standard for revision management in software development. Welder's version control functionality is based on this technology, with additional functionality to be able to handle projects with large files like 3D files. Secondly, Welder's interface is specifically designed to enable users to use this technology without any required technical knowledge or experience.

Version control provides users with an indefinite history of every file. Therefore, any change that has been made in a file can be reviewed and safely be restored.

The most powerful functionality of the version control system is that it provides this history for the project as a whole as well: in an instance, users can review any historical state of the project. This means that the version control system allows you to access, browse and inspect the files as if you travelled back in time and opened your project documentation at that historical date (see *Annex 2* for further details).

3.3 OPEN SOURCE

Technically Welder consists of a number of components:

- A front-end that displays the platform in the browser, and enables the users to interact with the system;
- An API that communicates between the front-end, the database, and the server that runs the version control software;
- 2 dedicated databases for storing large files and for storing images;
- A rendering engine for displaying 3D files in the browser;
- A desktop client; a piece of software users can install on their computer to help them with updating projects that have many files and are used frequently.

Figure 7: Diagram of Welder's system architecture

The software for these components is made open source; their source code is shared openly. This means anyone can inspect the software and submit improvements. Secondly, anyone can deploy their version of the software, and develop their functionality independent of Welder and Careables (for example, if someone wants to create and host a platform for different types of projects or a different purpose).

3.4 FUTURE STEPS

With the major functionality developed, future work is primarily incremental. Next iterations will optimize the user experience and performance of Welder.app. Improvements will be based on learnings from usage. Examples are: improving

the tags that are available to users and improving the functionality for adding an open source hardware license to a project.

One major planned feature is the addition of a search engine. With the current growth of projects on the platform this will become a necessary feature to enable users to find projects of their interest.

The Open Know-How working group - consisting of various organisations in the field of open source hardware - is developing an open standard for documenting and sharing projects, with the purpose to increase discoverability, portability, and translatability of knowledge relating to making hardware (physical objects). We are communicating with this workgroup, and intend to implement the standard into the platform as long as it is supportive of its purpose.

ANNEX

Annex 1: Personas and user journey

Annex 2: Welder Functionality

(The following visuals can also be accessed online [here](#))

Personas

Personas and journey

How to read the following pages

The platform must integrate with usual daily tasks performed by individuals.

The first step consists in defining who are our users and what they normally do.

The second step is to figure out how and where the platform can improve or modify these tasks.

Persona and Scenario

HP Researcher

Journey: Developing a research project

PRE

WHILE

CONCLUSION

Pre/while/conclusion:

the user journey map

He/she encounters a problem and starts searching. He/she:

- encounters a problem among his/her patients
- keeps up-to-date with the state of the art
- searches for fundings
- talks with collaborators
- starts a project

He/she works on the research project. He/she:

- keeps up-to-date with the state of the art
- uses tools to produce tests
- looks for external professionals in itinere
- tests his/her own hypotheses
- produces intermediate results
- talks with patients

He/she communicates and disseminates research results. He/she:

- disseminates the research results
- proposes a new solution to patients
- improves results following patient feedback
- starts a new research

Careables touch points:

how the platform integrate the user journey map

- presents itself through official communication channels used by HP (fairs, web sites, word of mouth...)

- presents its approach

- presents tools and techniques from a technical point of view

- informs about standards and laws

- supports on already available Careables

- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology

- supports in the research of useful tools and materials

- disseminates his/her project results

- tells the process

- gives the voice to researchers

- devotes a place for healthcare professionals on the platform so that they become part of careables network

Users and personas

At the stage we talk to **innovators** and **early users**, aware of the theme but with **no clear clues on how to start and develop** this type of projects.

Healthcare professionals
Therapists
or researchers

Caregiver
Parents

Care recipient
Person with disability

Maker
Designer

Institution
Foundation

HP Researcher

Who

Doctor working in the field of prosthetics in a medical hospital research center. In his/her work he/she is used to keep up-to-date with the newest research by means of official medical communication channels. He/she is used to work closely with patients but follows official medical intervention protocols (procedures/trials/tools...).

Needs

- finding funds and investors
- keeping continuously up-to-date on the state of art
- having flexible and fast tools at his/her disposal
- testing quickly his/her own hypotheses
- finding partners in itinere
- gaining the recognition for his/her research
- communicating the outcomes of a research

Objectives

- to produce better solutions and alternatives.
- **to create functional, comfortable and adaptable solutions for his/her different patients.**

Field: hospital, research center, lab

Journey: Developing a research project

PRE

WHILE

CONCLUSION

He/she encounters a problem and starts searching. He/she:

- encounters a problem among his/her patients
- keeps up-to-date with the state of the art
- searches for fundings
- talks with collaborators
- starts a project

He/she works on the research project.

- He/she:
- keeps up-to-date with the state of the art
 - uses tools to produce tests
 - looks for external professionals in itinere
 - tests his/her own hypotheses
 - produces intermediate results
 - talks with patients

He/she communicates and disseminates research results. He/she:

- disseminates the research results
- proposes a new solution to patients
- improves results following patient feedback
- starts a new research

- presents itself through official communication channels used by HP (fairs, web sites, word of mouth...)
- presents its approach
- presents tools and techniques from a technical point of view
- informs about standards and laws

- supports on already available Careables
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in the research of useful tools and materials

- disseminates his/her project results
- tells the process
- gives the voice to researchers
- devotes a place for healthcare professionals on the platform so that they become part of careables network

HP Therapist

Who

He/She works for a not-for-profit organisation delivering therapies for different neurological disabilities.

He/She has been active in the sector for years and works with patients who are very different from one other in terms of needs and capabilities. **His/Her patients usually look for alternative solutions themselves on the web and prefer those that provide also scientific papers/articles and an accurate and understandable documentation (video/images).**

His/Her relationship with patients and their families is direct and personal and **innovations or solutions are discussed together.**

Over the years he/she has always tried to improve the therapies, involving also new actors to tackle technological and technical challenges.

Needs

- improving therapies
- being at the forefront
- ensuring the well-being of patients and families
- reaching those in need
- making himself/herself understood by those who speak a non-medical language
- making patients and their families feel good

Objectives

- to help patients and families to free from physical and psychological limitations connected with disability
- to improve the lives of his/her patients
- **to find functional, comfortable and adaptable solutions for his/her different patients.**

Field: association, not-for profit organisation, a group of families, caregiver of one or more patients

Journey: Improving current therapies

PRE

He/she encounters a recurring problem during the therapies. He/she:

- works following established therapies
- tries to continually update his/her own approach
- tries to reach out to those in need
- doesn't know how to solve some problems of his/her job
- works closely with patients (empathetically)

WHILE

He/she looks for and/or develops a solution. He/she:

- keeps up-to-date with the state of the art
- searches for technical and certified support
- communicates continuously with his/her patients
- changes his/her approach gradually
- evaluates the improvement of therapies and the well-being of patients

CONCLUSION

He/she disseminates the results of the research. He/she:

- disseminates the research results
- proposes new solutions to patients
- improves results and solutions following patient feedback
- starts a new research
- modifies and hybridizes his/her approach to innovation within therapies adding what he/she learnt

- presents itself through official communication channels used by HP (fairs, web sites, word of mouth...)
- tells the stories of people and professionals
- presents tools and techniques that *are means rather than an end in themselves*.
- tells the eu project (methodology, eu framework of health and care sector)
- informs about standards and laws

- supports on already available Careables
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in the research of useful tools and materials
- gives voice to the change

- tells his/her story
- communicates the process
- gives voice to people involved
- devotes a place for healthcare professionals on the platform so that they become part of careables network
- publishes project results to help others

Caregiver Parents

Who

A couple with a son/daughter who has cognitive and motor disability. They blindly rely on decisions of their own doctor or specialist. They are necessarily used to change habits all the time to deal with their son/daughter's needs and, although stimulating, this also causes frustration and concerns.

They are looking for stability and security and, at the same time, they understand that it is necessary to stay in line with the time to live a better life.

Issue of costs? They have prejudices over the fact that therapies or alternative choices involve high costs.

Needs

- getting continuous support from experts
- being listened and guided
- sharing stories/difficulties
- keeping things light and normalizing
- being proactive and doing fun things
- **perceiving safety and reliability**
- **talking with other people who have similar needs**

Objectives

- to provide serenity for their son/daughter
- to minimize son/daughter's limitations.
- to undo prejudices about disability
- to find a place in the world for their own son/daughter

Field: home environment, everyday life, close relatives, family members (parents, sisters and siblings)

Caregiver Parents

Journey: Looking for an alternative solution

PRE

Their son/daughter does not feel well with the latest aid prescribed by the doctor. They:

- talk about it with family, friends and people who share the same difficulties
- discuss it with their doctor
- search online and contact the most popular aid manufacturers

WHILE

They search and/or adapt an alternative solution. They:

- benchmark products by assessing costs and features
- get in touch with new specialists
- discuss decisions continuously with doctor or other specialists
- try one or more alternative solutions

CONCLUSION

They adopt the solution and shares it with others. They:

- communicate their opinion and experience to other people in their situation.
- communicate their opinion to their doctor
- acquire a new approach to the research of solutions

- presents itself via familiar channels (social pages dedicated to disability, clinics, associations, HP)
- tells projects and stories where tools and techniques are contextualized
- tells eu project (careables and people)
- informs about standards and laws

- facilitates the research for existing solutions
- provides support for the implementation of Careables
- supports and intermediates between experts and non-experts
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in the research of useful tools and materials
- leads people in the process

- tells their story
- communicates the process
- gives voice to people involved
- devotes a place for caregivers on the platform so that they become part of careables network
- publishes project results to help others

Care recipient Person with disability

Who	Needs	Objectives
<p>She is a young mother with motor disabilities. She is used to change aids, looking for better solutions from time to time, but she always prefers the products available on the market. She is not an expert in technology but is familiar with the web (social media networks, web-searching, shopping, e-mail...). She is involved in the activities of an association linked to disability and thanks to it she discovers innovative projects. She would be enthusiastic to experiment with uncustomary solutions but she doesn't know how to do it. She's not used to look for alternative solutions online but, when she does so, she browses platforms dedicated to specific pathologies or national healthcare sites.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- being galvanized- not feeling different- having support from experts- having support from her circle (relatives/friends)- perceiving safety, reliability and honesty- receiving information in a clear language- having the possibility to customize an aid- using aesthetically likeable aids rather than unpleasant and stigmatizing ones- containing costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- To lessen the obstacles caused by disability- To be independent

Field: daily life (work, leisure, personal care, etc.), cognitive or physical disability

Care recipient Person with disability

Journey: Hacking an aid

PRE

She uses an aid that is not enough multipurpose. She:

- expresses her dissatisfaction and difficulties with her doctor, family, friends and people with the same experiences
- addresses to other experts
- searches autonomously for similar cases and people using the same language
- searches among main aid manufacturers and on official websites of healthcare institutions.

- presents itself via familiar channels (social pages dedicated to disability, clinics, associations, HP)
- tells projects and stories where tools and techniques are contextualized
- tells the eu project (careables and people)
- informs about standards and laws

WHILE

She finds an alternative solution. She:

- understands (resigns?) that the perfect solution does not exist in commerce
- runs into someone who has a very different approach from her own ie. hacking
- search among existing possibilities following this new approach
- experiments and faces uncertainties and unknown with her family members/doctor
- deepens the new knowledge acquired and the context she came across with
- continuously assesses validity and safety of these new solutions

- facilitates the research for existing solutions
- provides support for the creation of careables
- provides contact and intermediation with experts
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in the research of useful tools and materials
- leads people in the process

CONCLUSION

She uses the solution and is prepared to adopt again the approach if necessary. She:

- discovers new possibilities and opportunities to tackle his/her disability
- communicates her opinion and experience to other people in the same situation
- communicates her opinion to her doctor

- tells her story
- communicates the process
- gives voice to people involved
- devotes a place for her on the platform so that she becomes part of careables network
- publishes project results to help others

Maker Designer

Who

When needed, he/she pursues personal, work and commissioned projects by means of technologies of a fab lab or - more generally - a space for digital manufacturing. He/she can use various technologies and is not afraid to experiment with new ones, as well as with new software and programming languages.

He/she has never worked on projects in the social field or healthcare sector but knows the topics and would like to take a challenge even if he/she has no idea on how to do it.

He/she is used to look for and reproduce existing projects, adapting them to his/her needs and objectives.

The platforms he/she uses the most are those with an extended and active community, those facilitating the documentation of projects and thus general readability, and those without subscription costs.

Needs

- sharing projects and draft ideas
- being assisted by others like experts in prototypes' validation
- **making himself/herself understood by those who do not know his/her domain**
- learning, acquiring knowledge, being up-to-date
- **understanding technical fields and languages other than his/her own.**

Objectives

- to combine functionality with aesthetics
- to apply his/her expertise in new fields
- to create something useful and functional

Field: digital manufacturing and design

Maker Designer

Journey: Sharing a certified careable

PRE

He/she has developed a project that he/she considers useful for people in different areas of everyday life. He/she:

- discusses with the peers of the fab lab he/she usually attends
- discusses with external people recommended by peers. His/her problem is to carry out the research and verify the hypotheses in order to - eventually - share them on a larger scale.
- searches for Fablabs or other spaces that have made similar projects

- introduces itself (stories and projects) directly in the spaces where he/she hangs out
- uploads projects and shows up on more traditional platforms (e.g. Instructables)
- tells projects and stories where tools and techniques are contextualized
- tells the eu project (targets and activities)
- informs about standards and laws

WHILE

He/she needs to figure out how to certify and promote his/her project. He/she:

- uploads the project on common/known platforms
- receives/asks for feedback and comments on the project
- requires support of his/her trusted fablab/makerspace and/or others.
- gets in touch with experts and organisations outside his/her circle/sector.
- experiments with an approach that is different from the usual one based on designer/customer relationship

- facilitates the research for existing solutions
- provides support for the carrying out of careables
- provides contact and intermediation with experts to define project steps
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in the research of useful tools and materials
- leads people in the process of certification and documentation

CONCLUSION

He/she publishes the project. He/she:

- receives additional feedback from online communities
- discovers new research opportunities
- shares the acquired methodology in his/her own working environment

- tells his/her story
- communicates the process
- gives voice to people involved
- devotes a place for makers on the platform so that they become part of careables network
- publishes project results to help others
- involves him/her in other ongoing projects
- involves him/her in dissemination activities

Institution Foundation

Who

He/she is in charge of health&care/social department, managing grants for projects that have positive impact for citizens. He/she knows the geographical territory where the foundation operates: problems, opportunities, system of actors. Also, he/she knows the projects that have previously been funded, their challenges and critical aspects by monitoring the results.

He/she is aware that the financed projects are also a way to communicate, to establish root, to be visible on the territories, to fill the gaps of public entities facing cuts in social sectors.

He/she is used to not-profit logic because he/she interacts with that typology of subjects.

He/she is not particularly creative but always look for examples/ideas to be transferred to the local context. He/she is interested in the newest topics/issues and knows digital manufacturing technologies but has a limited view of their potential.

Disability is an issue that he/she particularly cares about: the ambition is to distance from ordinary projects with a limited impact over time.

Needs

- aligning with other similar subjects that have already been working on the topic of health/care/digital fabrication
- getting to know projects funded by other similar entities
- identifying who are the organisations behind projects and their reliability
- assessing the concrete activities carried out within projects and their limits
- finding simplicity and details .

Objectives

- . to position the institution as a leading innovation organisation
- . to measure impacts of innovation

Field: social, care, well-being, commons, citizenship, healthcare, social innovation.
They are stakeholders, namely organizations that by interest or power may influence the project, its implementation or its sustainability: subjects providing grants (e.g. banking foundations), public entities, legislative subjects, media, advocacy subjects (e.g. organizations for the rights of people with disabilities).

Journey: Evaluating a new approach to disability issues

PRE

He/she has to find a new intervention strategy about disability. He/she:

- knows the topic, the local framework and the stakeholders
- supports projects about disabilities
- monitors the development of projects and their results
- aware of the weaknesses of projects

WHILE

He/she looks for information and new approaches. He/she:

- . explores new fields and cross topics
- . maps best practises
- . gets in touch with experts/professionals outside his/her sector
- . comes in contact with organisations outside his/her sector

CONCLUSION

He/she decides to allocate budget for innovative projects. He/she:

- . acquires a new methodology/approach
- . inspires local actors to tackle disability issues differently
- . establishes partnerships with new actors

- presents itself through official communication channels and public events
- frames the eu healthcare context and its weaknesses
- tells the eu project (partners and aims)
- tells projects and stories where tools and techniques are contextualized

- explains co-design and other concepts
- offers (de)structured expertise and methodology
- supports in searching for useful tools and materials
- shows careables and their impacts on people's lives

- involves him/her in dissemination activities
- tells his/her new approach
- devotes a place for institutions willing to bring innovation in disability on the platform so that they become part of careables networks

Architecture

Home page

- Introduction to the project by highlighting the word "careable"
- Introduction to empowerment tools
- Introduction to solutions showcasing featured careables

Hereby 6 platforms regarding disability issues and making we have analysed as references.

About

What are the features that distinguish us?
What can we do for you? What can you do with us?

- Who we are (team and network)
- Where we are
- What we do
- What we provide
- How to get involved

Resources

This section regards all useful resources - both self-training and research - that allow individuals to acquire knowledge related to the creation of careables, to rules and regulations of medical devices and so on.

The resources are addressed to different users and regard not only methodology and technological aspects but also basics about empathic communication.

Principles
Methodology
Training Kit
How-to
Programs
Tools

The screenshot shows a website interface with a navigation bar at the top containing 'About', 'Resources', 'Stories', and 'Discover projects', along with a search icon. The main content area features a search query: 'I am a therapist and I'm looking for toolkits related to empathy'. Below the query, there are three resource cards. Each card consists of a dark blue square labeled 'Resource' and a light blue rounded rectangle containing text. The first card's text includes 'A chi serve?', 'A cosa serve?', and 'Dove ti porta?'. The second and third cards have three horizontal bars representing text. In the bottom right corner, there is a light blue circular button with the text 'need help?'.

Discover careables

This page anticipates the forwarding to Welder.app ("share" button)

It must clearly indicate to the users that they are about to switch to another platform and the reason.

This page is useful to explain that:

- you can explore uploaded careables
- you can replicate uploaded careables also thanks to support page
- you can upload a new project
- you can keep the documentation available on another platform by means of overview template

Help

This page explains how we support users (ie. training support and practical support on the carrying out of careables) and how they can get in touch with us.

How? Possible ways:

- Form
- Video tutorials
- FAQ
- Forums

The screenshot shows the help page of the Careable website. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for 'About', 'Resources', 'Stories', and 'Discover projects', along with a search icon. Below the navigation bar is a search input field with the placeholder text 'How can we help you?'. Underneath the search field is a list of help topics, each with a right-pointing chevron icon:

- I have a problem with a careable
- I have a problem with the resources
- I want to talk with someone *specificare chi sono i "someone"*
- I need to find something
- Glossary

At the bottom of the page, the email address 'careable@careable.org' is displayed.

[Welder.app/careables](https://welder.app/careables)

What is Welder.app

An open platform to share project's documentation to empower open communities, with file sharing and a version management solution.

Develop Better Hardware Together

Welder is a file sharing and version management solution, empowering both private teams and open communities.

Let nothing stop you from innovating

- Better organization of your project's files; always one clear latest revision.
- Review & retrieve any past moment in time, with unlimited project-wide revision history.
- Trace back past decisions and considerations using annotated revisions.

For private & public projects

- Join thousands of hardware developers contributing to open source hardware projects from around the world, or develop proprietary technologies with selected team members in private.

[VIEW PROJECTS](#)

Discover, Make, and Share

Design for care collection

Careables is an open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making.

Open Design of Trusted Things

OpenDoT is a PhD programme from the University of Dundee and Mozilla to explore how to build a more open, secure, and trustworthy Internet of Things. Technologists, designers, and researchers create and advocate for connected products that are more open, secure, and trustworthy.

Documentation

Documentation is a key aspect to share knowledge and replicate careables, both already existing solutions available on other platforms and new projects also co-designed together with us.

We have thought of two new documentation formats:

- 1-pager
- full documentation

1-pager

It is an agile format to collect the basic information of an existing external project and to link to its full documentation.

Summary

OpenBraille is a DIY Braille Embosser.

Most of the commercial machines are really expensive and emboss the dots by impacting the sheet. Instead of impacting and applying all the energy in a single hit, OpenBraille uses a physical encoder and a roller. In this way, the embossing is gradually done and the parts can be easily printed.

OpenBraille uses widely available parts on the market and components are originally used for 3D printers. The brain of the embosser is an arduino mega with a RAMPS board.

Goal

The assistive technology is very expensive: a mechanical braille embosser cost over a 1000\$USD and an electric goes from 3000\$ up to 5000\$. The designer, [ccampog7](#), couldn't find a DIY version, so he decided to make one himself to help one of his friend.

Glifo - writing tool

3d Printing Daily Living Fun/Leisure Learning/Communication

Overview

Files:	
> Files	
Assembly Guide	5 kB
glifo tutorial.pdf	168 kB

Summary

Glifo is a writing support tool used to help children with motor difficulties to draw and write independently. It was born from the co-design between Opendot fablab, TOG, Sara Monacchi, Andrea Pelino, Luca Toscano, therapists with kinesiological skills and families of children with disabilities.

Compared to the handles on the market Glifo works on the dorsal part of the hand, discouraging the contraction of the limb and making the drawing/writing activity effective in the school and home environment.

Created through parametric software and realized with digital fabrication, it is a customized solution for the user, functional, low cost, accessible, beautiful and therefore inclusive. It is light, washable and, thanks to 3d printing, adjustable for individual hand measurements!

If you need Glifo to be adapted to individual hand measurements, feel free to contact us!

UNICO – the Other Design is a brand of objects and design aids created by milanese Fab Lab Opendot and the TOG Foundation. The products are all custom-made and allow an improvement of the quality of life of children with disabilities. It is a project that aims to offer products and services for the production and sales of medical and orthopedic articles that are based on usefulness, specificity, sustainability and beauty, co-designed to satisfy the real needs of the individual. Co-design and digital fabrication become tools to tackle individual needs, shortening the distance between designer and end user.

Full documentation

It is the complete
step-by-step format
conceived for anyone
sharing his/her projects on
Welder or co-designed within
careables.

How to Document a Project

Creating a project

Project settings

Step 1: Meta data, and licencing:

Create Project

Project Settings

Thumbnail *

Title *

m
60 / 60

Description: Pitch your project in 90 characters or less. *

90 / 90

Tags: Categorize your project to make it easy to find.

▼

License: Choose what rights you grant others to copy, distribute, or modify your work.

▼

Privacy

- Public**
Anyone can see this project. You choose who can modify it.
- Private**
You choose who can see and modify this project.

CANCEL

CREATE

Creating a project

Project template

Step 2: Project template

Structure

1. Visuals
 - a. images
 - b. video
2. Summary
3. Goal
4. Specifications
5. Roadmap
6. Team
7. References

Create Project

Step 2/2

Project Overview

Media Gallery

IMAGES YOUTUBE

CHOOSE IMAGES

Summary: What is the product? * - Required

B I [List] [Link] [Image] [Video]

Type something

Goal: What does this project aim to accomplish

B I [List] [Link] [Image] [Video]

Type something

Specifications: what attributes describe the product?

Description	Metric	Units
<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>
<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>
<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>	<input type="text" value="50 / 50"/>

ADD SPECIFICATION

Roadmap: What future work is planned?

B I [List] [Link] [Image] [Video]

Type something

Team: Who worked on this project?

B I [List] [Link] [Image] [Video]

Type something

References: What external sources provide additional information?

Title	Link
<input type="text" value="200 / 200"/>	<input type="text" value="200 / 200"/>
Description	
<input type="text" value="300 / 300"/>	
Author(s) or name of external website	
<input type="text" value="200 / 200"/>	

ADD REFERENCE

CREATE

Creating a project

The result

Key elements:

1. Overview Page
2. File structure

Eyewriter

Creative Healthcare Learning/communication

ALONE FOLLOWING 3

Updated Oct 13, 2015

Overview

Files

- 3D STL files 418
- Assembly Guide 418
- The Eyewriter.pdf 210

Summary

Eyewriter is a low-cost eye-tracking apparatus + custom software that allows graffiti writers and artists with paralysis resulting from Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis to draw using only their eyes.

Members of Free Art and Technology (FAT), OpenFrameworks, the Graffiti Research Lab, and The Eberling Group communities teamed-up with a legendary LA graffiti writer, publisher and activist, named [REDACTED], to create the Eyewriter.

Tommy was diagnosed with ALS in 2003, a disease which has left him almost completely physically paralyzed... except for his eyes. The international team is working together to create a low-cost, open source eye-tracking system that will allow ALS patients to draw using just their eyes. The long term goal is to create a professional/social network of software developers, hardware hackers, urban projection artists and ALS patients from around the world who are using local materials and open source research to creatively connect and make eye art.

Version 2.0

The original design featured a pair of glasses as the basis for the eyewriter design. The new design, called "eyewriter 2.0," improves the accuracy of the device, and allows for people who's heads are moving slightly to also use an eye tracker. The original eyewriter, designed for a paralyzed graffiti artist (DRAFT), is designed to be worn on a completely motionless head.

The 2.0 design, which uses a camera and LED system mounted away from the head, can be used by people whose heads are moving slightly, such as MS patients, and people who wear glasses, etc.

This eyewriter system is cheap, and completely open source. At the moment, it costs about 200\$ in parts. Traditional commercial eye trackers costs between \$9000-\$20,000, so this is a magnitude of order cheaper, and is designed to help anyone who wants or needs an eyetracker.

In 2010 the eyewriter 2.0 was hooked it up to a robotic arm, to draw the artwork people make with their eyes.

References

Eyewriter software

The Eyewriter software is two parts -- an eye-tracking software designed for use with our low-cost glasses, and a drawing software designed for drawing with eye movements. The source code for the project is currently being hosted at: Google code

Eyewriter code on Github

Contains the original code for the Eyewriter

<https://github.com>

Eyewriter website

Contains information such as images, code, news, and background stories.

<http://eyewriter.org/>

Creating a project

File structure

File navigation & visualization

Overview

Files:

3D STL files	
End_block.stl	217 kB
Extension_arm.stl	47 kB
Glint_clip.stl	21 kB
Platform_clip.stl	108 kB
Picture folder	
Assembly Guide	4 kB
The-EyeWriter.pdf	2 MB

PREVIEW

Creating a project

File structure

Users can add:

1. Assembly guides
2. Files and folders
3. Texts

Overview

Creating a project

Assembly Guides

Guides which help users assemble the shared solutions.

Includes:

1. Images
2. Video's
3. Text

Steps:

Step 1 Start

- Tighten the countersunk screws M3x15 with a hexagon socket to assembly fingers to palm. To fix the fingers to the palm, go all the way to the bottom with the head of the screw without tightening it any more because the screw threading will damage the hole in the palm.

N° 10 screws M3x15
(N° 2 screws for each finger)

Step 2 Finger assembly

- Tighten the countersunk screws M3x8 with a hexagon socket to assembly the fingers. Don't screw the screws all the way down, let the pieces rotate (make sure that the pieces can rotate, but leave a slight friction). Proceed in this way for all the fingers.

N° 20 screws M3x8
(N° 4 screws for each finger)

Step 3 Rotation assembly

- Tighten the countersunk screws M3x15 with a hexagon socket to assembly the rotation system. Don't screw the screws all the way down, let the pieces rotate (make sure that the pieces can rotate, but leave a slight friction).

N° 2 screws M3x15

Creating a project

Assembly guides

Guide meta info

Includes:

1. Project difficulty level
2. Estimated development time
3. Components lists, including links

The screenshot shows a web interface for a project overview. At the top left, there is a navigation bar with a home icon and the text "Overview". Below this, a "Files:" section lists "Schematics", "STL Files", and "Assembly Guide" (which is highlighted in blue and has a "9 kB" size next to it). On the right side, there is a yellow plus icon. In the top right corner, there is a blue button labeled "FILE HISTORY" and two small icons (a printer and a trash can). The main content area is titled "Assembly Guide" and includes a difficulty level of "Advanced" and "Hours Required: 1". Below this, there is a "Components" section with a list of items and their quantities: Arduino Nano R3 (x1), Otto DIY Arduino NANO Shield I/O (x1), USB-A to Mini-USB Cable (x1), SG90 Micro-servo motor (x4), Buzzer (x1), Female/Female Jumper Wires (x6), 4xAA battery holder (x1), AA Batteries (x1), and Otto DIY 8x8mm Micro Switch Self lock On/Off (x1). At the bottom, there is a "Tools and Fabrication Machines" section listing a 3D printer and a Phillips Cross screwdriver.

Overview

Files:

- > Schematics
- > STL Files
- Assembly Guide** 9 kB

+

FILE HISTORY

Assembly Guide

Difficulty: Advanced Hours Required: 1

Components

Arduino Nano R3	x 1
Otto DIY Arduino NANO Shield I/O	x 1
USB-A to Mini-USB Cable	x 1
SG90 Micro-servo motor	x 4
Buzzer	x 1
Female/Female Jumper Wires	x 6
4xAA battery holder	x 1
AA Batteries	x 1
Otto DIY 8x8mm Micro Switch Self lock On/Off	x 1

Tools and Fabrication Machines

- 3D printer
- Phillips Cross screwdriver

Version control

File history

1. Explore every single file in a project
2. Explore its history
3. Revert back to any point in time

Author	Message	Date
richard+welder	Updated Overview.wevolver.	2019-02-21
richard+welder	Updated Overview.wevolver.	2019-02-21
undefined	form.values.message	2019-02-21

Version control

Project history

1. Explore the full project history
2. Revert the entire project to any moment in time
3. Continue working from a prior version

Project History			×
Author	Message	Date	
richard	uploading guide	2019-02-21	
richard	uploading guide 1 changed file ▾	2019-02-21	
richard	uploading guide 1 changed file ▾	2019-02-21	
richard	Updated Overview.wevolver. 1 changed file ▾	2019-02-21	
richard	Updated Overview.wevolver. 1 changed file ▾	2019-02-21	
undefined	form.values.message 1 changed file ▾	2019-02-21	

< 1 >

Step 2 Assemble the hand

Discovery

Discovery

Careables Project Page & category browsing

careables

Design for care collection

Careables is an open and inclusive approach to healthcare for citizens based on digital fabrication, distributed manufacturing and collaborative making.

www.careables.org

< [LEARNING/COMMUNICATION](#) [MOBILITY](#) [OUTDOOR INSTALLATIONS](#) [INDOOR INSTALLATIONS](#) [SELF CARE](#) [THERAPY](#) [DAILY LIVING](#) >

Open Trailer

3

Can be used as a shopping aid or for the pleasure of a riding companion.

[Daily Living](#) [Fun/leisure](#) [Mobility](#)

Moving3Dmachine

4

An adaptation for industrial sewing machines designed for people with disability.

[Daily Living](#)

Reading Aid

2

A device that allows to relax and read.

[Daily Living](#) [Learning/communication](#)

OpenBraille

1

a DIY Braille Embosser.

[Daily Living](#) [Learning/communication](#)

Helpers Helper

5

Practicing g-tube replacement procedures with a dummy.

[Self Care](#)

PillStorage Fits All

5

A parametric pillbox, divided in the days of the week.

[Daily Living](#) [Self Care](#)

Bike Adaptation

3

An attachment for children's bike for disabled children.

[Fun/leisure](#) [Outdoor Installations](#)

Finger Step Ladder

5

Therapy for shoulders by use of the fingerladder.

[Fun/leisure](#) [Therapy](#)

Push up bar

3

A workout tool for strenght .

[Fun/leisure](#)

Discovery

Similar projects

Featured at the bottom of each project, similar projects are show. The Welder platform selects these projects based on tags that users attach to each project.

support from [Parsons Communication Design & Technology](#).

The 2.0 device was designed with help and input from Takayuki Ito, Kyle McDonald, Golan Levin and students of the eyewriter collab at Parsons MFADT. Thanks also to the Studio for Creative Inquiry / CMU for hosting a session for development

Many thanks to: [Keith Pasko](#), [IMAK](#), [Eleanor Dank](#), [Jamie Wilkinson](#), and [Great Leach](#).

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References

[EyeWriter software](#)

The EyeWriter software is two parts -- an eye-tracking software designed for use with our low-cost glasses, and a drawing software designed for drawing with eye movements. The source code for the project is currently being hosted at: [Google code](#)

<https://code.google.com>

[EyeWriter code on Github](#)

Contains the original code for the EyeWriter

<https://github.com>

[EyeWriter website](#)

Contains information such as images, code, news, and background stories.

<http://eyewriter.org/>

Questions & Feedback

Respond as [Careables Org](#)

What's your question or feedback?

1500 / 1500

RESPOND

Eyewriter

Tags: [Careables](#) [Healthcare](#) [Learning/communication](#)

Similar Projects

Open Source Leg

A common hardware platform for comparison of control strategies.

[Bionics](#) [Healthcare](#) [Prosthetics](#) [Therapy](#)

Eyewriter

The EyeWriter is a low-cost eyetracking system.

[Healthcare](#) [Learning/communication](#)

Rollavie modified walker

redeveloping the walker to appeal to younger people.

[Healthcare](#) [Mobility](#)

Discovery

Questions and feedback

- Users can comment and give feedback
- Names are clickable and lead to users' profiles
- Users receive notifications when they receive comments

Questions & Feedback 2

Respond as **Edgar de Groot**

What's your question or feedback?

Edgar de groot

a few seconds ago

I love this project! I have access to al sorts of tools in my makerspace. How can I help?

Reply

Jack Strong

in 6 minutes

@edgar That's great Edgar. I'll drop you an email so we can collaborate on thi

Reply

Discovery

Questions and feedback

Comments in discussion threads trigger the notification system.

This example shows a notification a project creator receives when someone comments on their project.

Users can adjust and turn off the notification settings according to their preferences

The image shows a Gmail interface with a notification email. The left sidebar shows the Gmail navigation menu with 'Compose', 'Inbox' (6), 'Snoozed', 'Sent', and 'More'. The main content area displays an email from 'noreply@mail.wevolver.com' with the subject 'Wevolver - Someone else commented on Youbionic'. The email body contains a notification from 'Richard Hulskes' who commented on 'Youbionic'. It includes a timestamp 'On Feb 21, 2019 10:28 AM:' and a link to a YouTube video: 'https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fAfX4sDuo8Y'. Below the link is a button that says 'View the project on Wevolver.'. At the bottom of the email, there is a link to 'You can edit your email preferences on your account page.'. A small thumbnail image of a prosthetic hand is visible at the bottom of the email content.

Discovery

Profiles

Includes:

1. User's project section
2. Activity feed
3. Website and social media links

Edgar de Groot

Maker with interest in engineering

About

I'm a maker with a big interest in developing technologies for people with disabilities. I have access to 3d printers, lasercutters, and other specific tools needed for developing these types of technologies.

<https://www.edgardegroot.com/>

My Projects

Moving3Dmachine

An adaptation for industrial sewing machines designed for people with disability

ReadingAid

A device that allow to relax and read

[MORE](#)

Following

[PROJECTS](#) [TAGS](#)

The MAssist arm support

A wheelchair-mountable device to support users with reduced upper limb muscle strength

Youbionico Hand

3d printed bionic hand

[MORE](#)

Activity

Open Source Leg 23 Aug, responded:

These posts are seriously getting much better! Great job with this project!

[Reply](#)

Aramies 13 Jul, responded:

This has a very interesting choice of joint design. Physically feasible while the end result has similar motions to a four-legged animal. The video really makes the project astonishing.

[Reply](#)

System Architecture

